

MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES AS A WAY TO EFFECTIVELY TEACH FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Innovative the use of computer technology is not only a method of learning, but also a professional one it also appears as a means of forming powers. Teaching a foreign language a number of modern methods and functions of web search technology are distinguished detailed information is provided. This article also focuses on these aspects.

Key words: innovative educational technology, efficiency, professional empowerment, web search technology, socialization, knowledge activities.

МУЛЬТИМЕДИЙНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК СПОСОБ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

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Аннотация: Инновационное использование компьютерных технологий является не только методом обучения, но и профессиональным, оно выступает и как средство формирования способностей. При обучении иностранному языку выделяют ряд современных методов и функций технологии веб-поиска. В данной статье также уделяется внимание этим аспектам.

Ключевые слова: инновационные образовательные технологии, эффективность, профессиональные возможности, технология веб-поиска, социализация, познавательная деятельность.

Improving the effectiveness of the educational process is a matter of modern society problem, it is not only management, production, engineering, science and others the complexity of the tasks to be solved in the fields exists in Uzbekistan the general trend of the global development of the economic and social situation also related to To the concept of modernization of education in Uzbekistan accordingly, the main goal of professional education in higher education is at the level of world standards able to work effectively, competitive, competent, relevant level and is to prepare a qualified graduate of the profile. Training of professional personnel in the process of integration of the world community and the world of our country successful professional activity in the conditions of joining the trade-economic system the role of a foreign language, which is becoming a necessary condition for implementation is of urgent importance.

According to researchers, innovative technologies in the field of education creates great opportunities for active involvement of students in the educational process. Using innovative technologies, the educational process is not only about acquiring knowledge method, but also used as a means of forming professional skills [1]. The use of innovative technologies increases the knowledge activity of students, involves students in cooperation in the field of communication, and increases the level of socialization allows.

Regulate the educational process in the development of new educational technologies State shock institutions and teachers themselves as an educational task formation of the necessary computer skills, high level of students to achieve development and their enthusiasm for high-quality professional training rather than directly imparting knowledge such as increasing, teachers are involved.

Experience shows that the latest developments in the field of language teaching are different various technical devices to build the educational process with level interactivity and innovative systems.

Computer in the formation of educational competence approach the use of technology to individualize the educational process, materials to increase the clarity of presentation, i.e. visualization of education, various allows for a deep and comprehensive analysis of the processes occurring in the systems gives [2].

The following possibilities of computer technologies in the educational process clear: automation of education; appropriate computer modeling programs use as a means of demonstrating various processes; active learning systems (electronic textbooks, simulators, business simulation games, etc.) make it happen; access to databases; distance learning process. Not only the educational tasks to be solved in the formation of the necessary competences distinguishing, but also distinguishing educational methodology, from computer technologies in education methods of use [3]. Introduction of computer technology in education these aspects should be far from the last place, which is directed to a specific area encourages the development of educational systems. Co-temporary information in the field of education making the introduction of technologies more convenient and affordable, educational methods and organizational forms allows to change in terms of quality [4].

Innovative tools and teaching methods include: web quests, online training, video conferencing, open source policy ("distributed" development principle), method of specific situations, virtual reality technology.

Web search is a challenging task with elements of role-playing games information resources of the Internet are used to increase. Webquest (Web Quest) The term was first coined in 1995 by the University of San Diego (USA) in educational technology suggested by Professor Bernie Dodge. The author has different levels of education innovative for integration into the educational process in teaching different educational subjects Developed Internet programs. Kenton Letkeman, a series of educational webquests The creator believes that this is a "super-educational tool". constructive approach to education is used.

Students prepare answers or solutions when doing web quests can't, they solve the task assigned to them independently.

So to work on a web quest: to organize an active independent or group search activity helps; helps develop creative thinking and problem solving skills; allows for a personal approach; thinking teaches skills (explanation, comparison, classification, general and specific). Creating a webquest requires a high level of subject matter, methodological and informational communication skills from a teacher. The topic of web quests is the most diverse possible, problem tasks may vary in complexity.

In journalistic web quests (journalistic tasks), students gather facts and they should organize them in a report, interview or other journalistic genre. Design The web quest (design task) pre-defined the students in a certain framework requires a product creation or action plan to accomplish the goal.

For example, planning a kitchen that meets the needs of a particular family or planning to find a job and graduate from a college, etc. Creative web quests (creative products task) are given to students in a certain format (Fig. game, poster, game, song, website, multimedia presentation, etc.) any requires creating a product. Creative projects are similar in design, but theirs the results will be more free and difficult to predict. Solve controversial problems Web quests (consensus building task) are different, sometimes contradictory seeking and presenting opinions on the same issue and bringing them to consensus involves trying to go.

Persuasive web quest (persuasive task) has its own goal, to convince someone creates a product that can convince you of something. Such a task is from the usual retelling goes out and leads students to the materials obtained in working with the claim requires the development of evidence to support any statement, opinion, option to solve the problem based on. of such a project the final product may be a letter, article, press release, video recording, multimedia presentation, web page, etc.

Self-learning web quests (self-learning tasks) With the aim of students to better understand themselves, they are online research can develop through Such projects are rare, but there are examples still available, such as web quests, future careers and jobs for students aimed at studying Internet resources related to dealing with Analytical web search (analytical task) in the real world as part of this topic examines the interdependence of things. Such assignments give students one or to study several things carefully and find similarities and differences, as well as calculating the hidden meaning of these similarities and differences, the reason and to understand the relationship of consequences and discuss their significance creates the ground [5]. For example, the cultures of two countries or peoples not to identify their similarities and differences in the comparison, but their thinking and speculating about what it means about causes and effects should be done.

Assessment web quests (judgment tasks) present students with a range of topics and the requirement to evaluate or classify them or choose a solution from a large list will be done. Often, but not necessarily, students in such assignments, e.g. judges are encouraged to participate in a mock trial. Scientific web quests (scientific tasks) to introduce and acquaint students with scientific research in various fields serves. The topic of web quests can be the most diverse, problematic tasks may vary in complexity.

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